

ANNEX A - SURVEY

Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage

The DIGITAL ICH Observatory is conducting a survey on Inventories & Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH). With this survey we intend to study the practices and opinions of users of ICH inventories.

This survey refers to the different domains of ICH - oral expressions (legends, folk tales, traditional songs ...); arts and crafts; social practices, celebrations and rituals; performing arts (popular theatre, traditional dance...) and knowledge and practices related to nature and the universe.

This survey is anonymous. No information about your identity is asked. The data will only be used for statistical treatment. Estimated time to answer: less than 15 minutes.

***Required**

1. *

Tick all that apply.

I agree to participate and I will only reply once.

To make sure you are not a robot...

2. Type the characters you see above *

You, ICH & Inventories

3. Your relation with INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE (ICH) (choose 1 option, the one that best fits your situation) *

Mark only one oval.

- I practice traditions (crafts, dance, music, celebrations, traditional knowledge ...)
- I work on intangible cultural heritage
- I study on intangible cultural heritage
- I am curious and I like to know/see expressions of intangible cultural heritage
- I have an opinion on matters of intangible cultural heritage
- I am not related to intangible cultural heritage
- Other: _____

4. Your relation with INVENTORIES of intangible cultural heritage (ICH Inventories) (choose 1 option, the one that best fits your situation) *

Mark only one oval.

- I practice traditions that have been inventorying
- I work on inventories of intangible cultural heritage
- I study on inventories of intangible cultural heritage
- I am curious and I like to use inventories of intangible cultural heritage
- I have an opinion on matters of intangible cultural heritage
- I am not related to inventories of intangible cultural heritage
- Other: _____

5. Do you know the 2003 UNESCO CONVENTION for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage? *

Mark only one oval.

- I don't know
- I've heard about it
- I know badly
- I know
- I know very well

Skip to question 6

Socio & demographic characterization (1)

6. Country of residence *

Mark only one oval.

7. Age *

Mark only one oval.

- Up to 20 years
- 21 to 40 years
- 41 to 60 years
- 61 years or more

8. Sex *

Mark only one oval.

- Female
- Male

9. Residence area *

Mark only one oval.

Urban

Rural

10. Education *

Mark only one oval.

Primary school

High school

Academic degree (Associate, Bachelor, Master or Doctoral)

Other: _____

11. Current occupation *

Mark only one oval.

Employee

Independent worker

Student

Retired

Unemployed

Other: _____

Socio & demographic characterization (2)

12. Your work sector (choose 1 option) *

Mark only one oval.

- I'm not working
- Industry
- Agriculture
- Trade
- Education, science or culture
- Public administration
- Other Services

13. Your professional group (choose 1 option) *

Mark only one oval.

- I'm not working
- Entrepreneur
- Intellectual and scientific specialist
- Administrative
- Technical or operational worker
- Unqualified

14. Entity where you work (choose 1 option) *

Mark only one oval.

- I'm not working
- Private company
- State - National Administration
- State - Regional or local administration
- NGO
- University or Research Center
- Other: _____

Your practice & ICH inventories (1)

15. How many inventories of intangible cultural heritage (ICH inventories) have you consulted? *

Mark only one oval.

- none
- 1
- 2 to 4
- 5 to 7
- 8 to 10
- more than 10

Your practice & ICH inventories (2)

16. How often do you check ICH inventories? *

Mark only one oval.

- Every day
- At least once a week
- At least once a month
- At least once a year
- I haven't used for years

17. In normal access, how much time do you spend on an ICH inventory? *

Mark only one oval.

- Up to 5 minutes
- Up to 15 minutes
- Up to 30 minutes
- Up to 1 hour
- More than 1 hour

18. Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are in what language? *

Mark only one oval.

- In my country's language
- English
- In another Language

19. Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are: *

Mark only one oval.

- Transnational
- National
- Regional
- Local

Your practice & ICH inventories (3)

20. Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are about (choose 1 option): *

Mark only one oval.

- Oral traditions and expressions
- Performing arts
- Social practices, rituals and festive events
- Knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe
- Traditional craftsmanship
- All the domains mentioned above

21. On average, how many traditions are inscribed in the ICH Inventories you consult? *

Mark only one oval.

- up to 10
- 10 to 50
- 50 to 100
- more than 100
- I don't know

22. Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are promoted by: (choose 1 option) *

Mark only one oval.

- Private company
- State - National Administration
- State - Regional or local administration
- ICH practitioners, NGOs, local associations, individuals or other informal groups
- University or Research Center
- UNESCO Organization
- I don't know
- Other: _____

23. Most of the ICH Inventories you consult are: *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes	No	I don't know
Online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Open access	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Public	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Updated	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Have a call for participation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Your practice & Usability

24. When I use an ICH Inventory: (choose the frequency by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Many times	Always
I visit only the front page	<input type="radio"/>				
I explore multiple pages	<input type="radio"/>				
I know what I'm looking for	<input type="radio"/>				
I explore by menu	<input type="radio"/>				
I explore by links	<input type="radio"/>				
I explore by search	<input type="radio"/>				

25. When I explore contents in an ICH Inventory: (choose the frequency by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Many times	Always
I read texts	<input type="radio"/>				
I watch videos	<input type="radio"/>				
I listen to soundtracks	<input type="radio"/>				
I look at photos	<input type="radio"/>				

26. About social media, in an ICH Inventory: (choose the frequency by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Many times	Always
I use their social media	<input type="radio"/>				
I share info on my social media	<input type="radio"/>				

Your practice & Search

27. When I search in an ICH Inventory: (choose the frequency by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Many times	Always
I use simple search	<input type="radio"/>				
I use advanced search	<input type="radio"/>				
I search by location	<input type="radio"/>				
I search by ICH domain	<input type="radio"/>				
I search by keyword	<input type="radio"/>				

Your practice & Participation

28. About participation, in an ICH inventory: (choose the frequency by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Many times	Always
I leave comments	<input type="radio"/>				
I participate in forums	<input type="radio"/>				
I contact for questions	<input type="radio"/>				
I participate with contents	<input type="radio"/>				
I subscribe to "communities"	<input type="radio"/>				
I subscribe to newsletters	<input type="radio"/>				

29.

Have you ever participated in an ICH Inventory? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Yes	No
Participating in public sessions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participating in plenaries or assemblies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participating in debates	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participating in capacity-building/Workshops	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Your opinion & Importance (3)

34. What information should be available in an ICH inventory? (choose the importance by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not Important	Less important	So-so	Important	Very important
Tradition name	<input type="radio"/>				
Practitioners info	<input type="radio"/>				
Short description of the tradition	<input type="radio"/>				
Detailed Description of the tradition	<input type="radio"/>				
ICH History	<input type="radio"/>				
ICH Threats	<input type="radio"/>				
Safeguard plan	<input type="radio"/>				
Videos	<input type="radio"/>				
Sounds	<input type="radio"/>				
Usual photos	<input type="radio"/>				
360° photos	<input type="radio"/>				
Streaming sessions	<input type="radio"/>				
Access to Virtual Reality/Augmented Reality	<input type="radio"/>				
Methodology/team info	<input type="radio"/>				
Community consent	<input type="radio"/>				
Mention UNESCO Convention	<input type="radio"/>				
Intellectual rights	<input type="radio"/>				

36. What is important in a participatory ICH inventory? (choose the importance by item) *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not Important	Less important	So-so	Important	Very important	No opinion
To allow voluntary contributions	<input type="radio"/>					
To have a call for contributions	<input type="radio"/>					
To give instructions for contributions	<input type="radio"/>					
To be easy to fill in	<input type="radio"/>					
To have moderators	<input type="radio"/>					
To provide technical support	<input type="radio"/>					
To use participatory techniques	<input type="radio"/>					

The survey ended. Please submit. Thank you for your participation.

37. Control question - Is this the 1st time you answer this survey? *

Tick all that apply.

Yes

No

38. How do you evaluate the fulfillment of this survey? (choose 1 option)

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very difficult	<input type="radio"/>	Very easy				

39. Comments

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